

Stakeholders Engagement – S3C Project

Results of qualitative study

August, 2015

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Executive Summary

Stakeholders' attitude towards energy efficiency

1. Among stakeholders, there are different degrees of involvement in energy and environment related themes. The highest levels of involvement were noticed in environmental related departments of Alcochete's City Hall. These stakeholders point out mainly environmental and political gains that derive from the implementation of smart meters. Stakeholders that have shown to be less involved with these themes focus more on short-term gains and immediacy of the results, remaining the "saving money" argument as the most impactful benefit of energy efficiency.
2. Despite this, all stakeholders feel that it is crucial to develop a closer work with the population to increase its environmental and energy-saving consciousness. Alcochete City Hall developed a lot of initiatives to be closer to the population (some of them together with EDP) with a special focus on children, who play a major role in bringing home information and changing behaviours. An example is the successful case of recycling adoption by Portuguese families.

The present of InovGrid project

3. Overall, EDP is seen as major partner of Alcochete City Hall and the InovGrid project is a good example of this fruitful partnership. This is recognized as an important project as it can leverage the image of the region and also the daily life of its people.
4. The installation of the EDP Boxes (smart meters) was a landmark of this project, and its benefits are well recognized: the EDP Box provides a greater control over expenses, it allows the customers to change their contracted power and make other contractual changes online; and it is expected to enhance the quality service in terms electricity supply (with less power cuts); it's a sign of progress and vision.
5. There are however some challenges with the project roll out that need to be addressed, namely: (i) The City Hall needs to have more information, to answer population doubts, about the current status of meter installation.

Executive Summary

6. Challenges within the population are related more with the fact of not having the person responsible for the energy contract home in the moment of installation or with people not reading the leaflets. In sequence, people felt they don't have enough information and create some false expectations, that ultimately can't be fulfilled. The message of potential money saving through changing habits wasn't understood in its fully meaning. People were expecting to reduce costs, even without changing behaviors.
7. Regarding stakeholders role there's clearly two different levels of involvement with InovGrid project, depending on the information stakeholders have about the project and also the degree of direct contact with EDP. City Hall and stakeholders in more regular and direct contact with EDP refer a very positive and open relationship. Other stakeholders who report to not having a frequent relationship with EDP are open to increase their level of participation in the project as they feel that they can have an important role on reaching the population.
8. And in fact, achieving a positive word-of-mouth towards this project greatly depends on a well-organized closeness policy. Alcochete is a very traditional and cohesive council, people have the habit of directly approaching their elected representatives and tend to trust them more than other (non local) institutions. This behavioural trace is seen in smaller cities and communities throughout Portugal, where people really tend to buy-in to participate in a project if it is promoted by their region/city local institutions.
9. Regarding the specific initiatives done so far by EDP, overall they are seen as positive. The "Information Session" was useful because it allowed people and less involved stakeholders to get more information and to clarify some misunderstandings. The "S3C game" is seen as useful in terms of educating the population. And the "Exhibition" was perceived as a way of recognizing Alcochete people.
10. For the conference in October stakeholders suggest to announce it in a way that can attract several segments of the population. They also recommend to show the international acknowledgement and reward all the efforts done so far, within the project.

Executive Summary

The future of InovGrid project

11. As a future step of InovGrid project it's important to increase the information, within the population, by clarifying when will the meters be fully operating and enhance the meter's functionalities by reminding them of the advantages for their daily life's; by making sure they understand well the advantages that the new meter provides; by using clear and simple messages; by making them feel safe (as there is also some degree of anxiety towards any change).
12. Increasing stakeholders engagement is basically a matter of a more frequent and systematic feedback and a continuous support. Stakeholders expect to be constantly informed and involved in what is happening and in what is planned to happen. They welcome EDP's participation in other planned initiatives and other projects and feel it's important to acknowledge their relevant contribution to this project.
13. Increasing the population engagement requires a multidimensional strategy: to be close and clear are the key words. It's important to promote a policy of closeness, by organizing several small information sessions at parish councils, City Hall departments with direct contact with the population, local collectivities and neighbourhoods. Also, local stakeholders can help to bridge the relationship between the population and EDP, specially after the installation of the meters to let them know what are the most relevant and frequent questions that stand out.
14. And in the other hand, it's important to be clear in order to attract people and inform them in a light and pragmatic way. Introduce InovGrid project in some school disciplines (Geography, English, project area) and activities, across all year, including the smaller children, could be also an option to optimize the effects of this project.

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Overall, there are different degrees of involvement in energy and environment related themes, being this higher in environmental related departments of the City Hall.

Attitudes towards environment

City Hall Stakeholders, whose departments are more involved with the environment, have a broader perspective of the gains related to energy efficiency / nature protection.

Significant environmental gains

- **Save resources** and protects future generations
- **Reduce CO2 emissions** and meet international targets (e.g. Kyoto Protocol)
- **Preserve the rich natural heritage of Alcochete region**

"Energy efficiency is vital if we want to keep the world around us... Not only to save natural resources, but also to keep our ecosystems and our biodiversity. This is really important for our future generations."

"To improve life conditions, cost reduction is one of the main associations, ... but also allowing a better life in the planet and, and CO2 reduction is of utmost importance."

"80% of our territory is a protected area. And we have to protect it."

Economical and political gains

- **Allows the families to save money**, by optimising their electricity and water consumption habits
- **Development of Alcochete region**, by attracting active upper middle class population and visitors
- **Increase Alcochete's visibility** at a national level (a role model)
- **Projection of the executive good work** in finding an optimal balance between respecting nature/traditions and a progressive vision (modernity and innovation)

"A change of attitude... adopting more environmentally friendly behaviours... This will not only impact on our bills but also at a more global level."

Stakeholders less involved with these themes see the energy efficiency more as a way to save money and less associated to intangible gains.

Stakeholders less involved with these themes have a different perspective, more focused on short-term gains.

A reductionist perspective of energy efficiency

- **Focus on short-term gains** and immediacy of the results
- **Saving money argument remains by far the most impactful**
- **This can be caused by the lack of information or interest**

"Saving money, turning off the lights."

"Changing old habits... of having everything connected at the same time and consuming energy."

Little sensitivity to the importance of environmental sustainability (focus in near future)

- **Less sensitive to non monetary, less tangible gains** – like protecting the environment and saving natural resources
- **A distant concern**, somebody else's problem, they have more important daily concerns to think about

"We have a long way to go, it's very difficult to awake a global conscience among the citizens."

Regardless of their own involvement with the theme, all stakeholders agree that it is fundamental to develop a closer work with the population.

Attitudes towards environment

Besides the natural resistance to change there is still a problem of lack of information specially among the elderly and the least resourceful population.

Globally, the following **targets are the most resistant to change:**

- Elderly population living in the more traditional part of the city;
- Underprivileged population;
- People that receive the minimum income allowance;
- Population with a low education level;
- Rural area /specially the outskirts of the city;

"We find the greatest resistance in the historical core of the city, the older part of the city where there were no recycling habits for instance."

"Our public housing beneficiaries have extremely high electricity, water and bills. ... we try to explain to them some habits during our visits in order to reduce consumption... And some start to have some concerns about it."

"You only have to look at the typical profile of the Portuguese population, not everybody is changing contracts through a smartphone..."

People that hardly come to information sessions, don't read e-mails / letters and have a quite suspicious attitude toward strangers, need a more direct contact.

It's essential to **be closer** to reach the population and the information needs to be easily understood (simple and clear) mainly for elderly and underprivileged population

"Small groups work best in Alcochete, we talk to families and they spread the word in the building or in the neighbourhood."

Alcochete City Hall has made over the years several efforts / initiatives to increase environmental and energy-saving consciousness in the population.

Attitudes towards environment

Currently, Alcochete City Hall is well-aware of the importance of preserving the region's great natural patrimony. In sequence they've developed several initiatives to stimulate energy saving and recycling behaviours.

It's clear the involvement of **children and families** in these activities:

European Mobility Week (together with S. Energia)

- People have fun using alternative means of transportation;
- Attracts the whole family;

"All the initiatives that took place during the European mobility week... we had bicycles and non polluting means of transportation, we exchange garbage for public transportation tickets so that people use them more often... People liked it a lot, it was a major success."

Activities for children (all year)

- There are several activities for children: games to allow for environmental education, recycling, vegetable garden, children's day commemoration activities;

"Kids love the day without cars, they make their parents mark it on their agendas."

S3C online game

- Immediately comes to mind as a positive initiative among stakeholders in the education area;
- City Hall has recently communicated the game at the children's holiday camp and it seems to appeal to younger children.

It's important to **involve children** when aiming to a greater change of behaviour.

"The best way to get to parents and educate adults is through the children."

Alcochete City Hall has made a great investment in replacing lightning equipment, to save energy and give an example of energy efficiency to Alcochete population.

Attitudes towards environment

More cost-effective and eco-friendly equipment and procedures have been an asset of the current Alcochete executive.

Covenant of Mayors

- **Alcochete has joined the Covenant of Mayors and committed to reduce CO2 emissions**
- There was some work done together with the Energy Agency, but this partnership has recently ended due to financial constraints

"We adhered to the Covenant of Mayors. It is a European initiative and our county also joined. What we have proposed in accordance with the Covenant of Mayors is to reduce CO2 emissions by 20% until 2040."

Replacing public lighting systems

- **Replacement of traditional street lamps by LED equipment and astronomical clocks** that allow to save a great amount of energy
- **Main driver is economical** (to reduce public expenses) but there are also social and political gains involved, in terms of increasing projection of Alcochete region

"Through the years we've done a vast number of energy efficiency measures, not just electricity, but also water."

"When it was implemented it was estimated to have a 3% reduction of cost."

"We are a pioneer county and friend-county of EDP in these initiatives."

"EDP is a partner in replacing all public illumination."

EDP is seen as major partner in this changing process since EDP also participate in this initiative by replacing traditional street lamps by LED and all the help provided is very welcomed.

The **InovGrid project** is a **good example** of this **fructuous partnership**.

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Current executive welcomed the InovGrid project and acknowledged its importance as an opportunity of development for Alcochete region since its very beginning.

Importance of InovGrid

From the start, Alcochete City Hall had a great interest in participating in this project, as it can both benefit the image of region and the life of its inhabitants.

InovGrid:

- Allows for economic development – nature friendly tourism and a nice residential area near Lisbon;
- Projects a pioneer image of the council;
- Differentiate Alcochete , when applying to European funds or public project financing.

“InovGrid is, without a doubt, an added-value for us, a state of the art that fully fits the City Hall strategy.”

“The InovGrid project is an asset, we are the first Council of Lisbon Metropolitan area to take part in the InovGrid Project.”

“Conveys a positive image of the Council.”

Overall EDP is seen as a **valuable partner**, as it can give a valid contribution for the region’s development.

“We were interested from the start and Alcochete region had the ideal characteristics for this project.”

“We have an excellent relationship with EDP.”

“EDP looked at us as a county that had all the necessary characteristics to launch this project in its entirety (...) A good vision EDP had with regards to Alcochete and that we welcomed promptly.”

Specially among those who know better this project, InovGrid is seen as an innovative and worthwhile project.

Importance of InovGrid

Its positive impact can and is expected to reach the people's daily lives.

- By implementing the future of electricity meters (EDP box), Alcochete people are one of the very first to **gain access to several advantages**:
 - **Saving money** through a more rational consumption of electricity and greater awareness of energy waste;
 - **Convenience** – the counting is done automatically.
- Besides this the project helps the executive to educate the population in adopting more eco-friendly and overall rational behaviours
 - A **more rational usage** of resources (in this case electricity)
 - Leverages in the common citizen a more **environmental responsible attitude** which benefits all
- **Also, means greater satisfaction** of the population regarding their representative's decisions. And in last instance, the opportunity to be chosen as well in the next electorate.

"There is a big change of concepts, from a passive to an active role... we consumers play an active role in our energy consumption, and we must make choices in order to reduce it, we (consumers) have a more decisive role..."

"It's a project that allows to educate consumers... makes them more disciplined and checking their consumptions."

**Improving the
quality of life of
the citizens**

The installation of EDP Box was a landmark that reinforced stakeholders interest in the project, since it has various advantages.

Importance of InovGrid

- Real time counting is the most notorious advantage among the population.
- **It is quite valued:**
 - less effort (it's done automatically);
 - provides a greater control over expenses and means the end of unpleasant surprises with the electricity bill.
- **At a different level, it's also a sign of progress and vision.**

Main advantage

"People like the idea of having a more regular bill and look forward to not having estimates or monthly cost oscillations in their EDP invoices. It's real, you only pay for what you have used."

"The main advantage is real time counting because estimates can be disturbing. A significant percentage of people lives on a tight budget."

"These meters will allow a digital reading, a long range reading and computerised control.. So no one has to go at home and read them..."

"Allows people to pay just the real cost, not an estimate."

"They are the future, it's just a matter of time and all of us will have one at home..."

EDP box has also other assets, but only a small part of the population are aware of them (mainly younger, educated, middle upper class citizens).

Importance of InovGrid

There are also other advantages recognized but they are less popular among the population in general:

- ✓ Change contracts online
- ✓ Greater control
- ✓ Quality of service

- Being able to **change potency and making other contractual changes online;**
- **Having a greater control** as a consequence of monitoring the household energy consumptions;
- **Also allows to offer a good (substituir por better) quality service in terms electricity supply (with less power cuts).**

"These are more advanced and it's going to affect only people more comfortable using new technologies..."

"Have greater control over the energy consumptions and adjust according to times of greater consumption..."

"Smart Grids allow a greater control of the power cuts... and they can quickly solve the problem."

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Main challenge felt by the City Hall is to have more information regarding EDP Box roll out process, as the population has some doubts.

Challenges within the project

As the people working in the City Hall are somewhat close to the population, sometimes they are asked questions, for which they don't have enough information to answer.

Basically, the stakeholders feel they need to have more information regarding:

“At the moment people are asking: when does this start counting directly and we start to receive the real invoices (not estimates)?”

- *What is the current status of meter installation? By when will all meters be installed?*
- *In which areas the meters are already functioning?*
- *When will the estimates end?*
- *What strategies should they use when people don't know how to handle these equipment or being suspicious about them, or mad because they had a cost increase?*

The major challenges are caused by the lack of information and misunderstandings within the population.

Challenges within the project

Within the installation, there were some challenges (as not having the person responsible for the energy contract or people not reading the leaflets), which originates people to feel they don't have the needed information and also some misunderstanding and erroneous expectations.

Lack of information

- **People aren't sure** if the meters are already working or not
- **Some have doubt how to provide the counting to EDP**
- **The box was installed, they've received a leaflet and a magnet, but feel the need to further verbal explanation**
- **Many don't know what the advantages are and fear a cost increase from EDP** (following negative word-of-mouth originated from other people's experiences)

"Some people thought it was already working and they didn't had to no more provide their counting to EDP..."

"All the people I talked about this, told me I don't understand how its done"

"I believe that many people have these boxes at home and don't know how to use them."

Misunderstanding and erroneous expectations

- **Many people made a superficial reading of being able to save money** with these new boxes - some expected a cost decrease in their electricity bill
- But **some citizens had to deal with a price increase instead**, (originated by a more accurate reading or because the meter was installed in a period where the electricity consumption was higher) **and strongly complained about it.**

"Is it going to be cheaper, not cheaper..., is this going to be really a benefit for all of us?"

"Some people complained: "My bill increased since they putted the new meter!"

And the message of potential money saving through changing habits wasn't understood in its fully meaning.

Challenges within the project

People were expecting to reduce costs, even without changing behaviors.

- **The message of saving money didn't come across fully** – people anchored more in the 'saving money' part rather than on the 'changing habits' part
- **There was eventually some misunderstanding in the installation process**, since some people thought they no longer had to provide counting to EDP or receive estimates (and they have to do it while the system is not fully operational)
- **The instalment of these boxes coincided with the changes of the liberated market** so costs increased but due to market changes and not the new meters
- **People often have a suspicious attitude towards EDP**, referring the high profits and the dissatisfaction regarding costs

"People expected to pay less because they had and 'intelligent' meter ... people expect new technologies to help them reduce their bills. When what is happening is just the other way around: changing habits and behaviours will have a positive impact on the household bills, and not the meter in itself."

"A lady told me that the installer told her that she no longer had to make the counting."

"The installation of meters coincided with the beginning of the liberalized market, so we had many people complaining about the cost increase and blaming the new meter for this... People say things like my electricity bill doubled or tripled!"

It's important that EDP clarifies how people can save money with the EDP box and find ways to explain how they can do the readings themselves, while the automatic counting system isn't fully operational

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There are different role perceptions according to the knowledge stakeholders have of this project and the degree of interaction with EDP.

Achieving a **positive word-of-mouth** towards this project greatly **depends on a well-organized policy of closeness**. Alcochete is a very traditional and cohesive council, people have the habit of directly approaching their elected representatives and tend to trust them more than other (non local) institutions.

City Hall and stakeholders in more regular and direct contact with EDP refer a very positive and open relationship.

Stakeholders' involvement

This group of stakeholders **reiterate the good partnership with EDP** and refer a close and quite informal relationship:

- An easy and informal contact that facilitates communication;
- EDP is a partner in more than one City Hall initiative (see it as a long-term partnership);
- The help to install the public LED illumination established a good solid path and stakeholders expect more and more synergies in the future.

"We have been working quite well together, it has been an excellent partnership, we are very articulated ... There's not an institutional weight attached, we just pick up the phone and talk."

"EDP has been a good partner, we meet periodically and exchange impressions at the highest level, they are very receptive and I think they like coming to Alcochete and talk to us as well."

"We feel that EDP has good will and there's, above all, mutual trust. And this is fundamental."

To improve their involvement, these stakeholders would like to have regular updates and to know in advance EDP's plans regarding this project and related EDP initiatives.

Stakeholders' involvement

For this stakeholders their involvement would improve with more information, during the roll out of the process. This would mean more control and being able to plan in advance.

- **So they can correctly inform people** who approach them
- **Convey realistic expectations** regarding its advantages
 - **Quantifying the gains** would help them support these messages (research data from EDP)
- **Also need help regarding spreading the correct information to a greater number of people**, and developing further initiatives that would involve people in a positive way
- **Are available to provide a regular and systematic feedback** regarding how people are reacting and what must be improved during the several stages of the project

"According to last information session, 90% of the boxes were installed and only 10% allowed the remote reading (...) we would like to be kept informed throughout the process (...) if everything is according to plans, timings, covered areas..."

"I remember that it was said that the implementation of these boxes could mean an energetic saving of 3% but I had no further information regarding this... Does this equipment allow a saving of around 3% or not..."

"There's work to be done, perhaps EDP could transmit some information through their invoices... To help us to disseminate the information and enlighten citizens."

"We have some feedback we could share with EDP... This could be done in connection with the presidential office and through our communication department.... We can also talk to local collectivities, IPSS..."

It's fundamental to increase the participation of other stakeholders, that are closer to different and difficult segments of the population, namely the elderly, rural areas and lower social class.

Stakeholders' involvement

This group of stakeholders overall shows a more distanced attitude towards EDP - see it as a good partner for the executive but admit not having much information about the project.

Are open and feel they can have a more important role in the process

- **Parish councils** can have a major role in spreading the right messages to smaller and secluded rural areas of Alcochete Council
- **City Hall education and social support departments** can have a more **pedagogic action** and encourage local collectivities to be involved – there are many in Alcochete and people tend to trust them
- **Schools can have and are willing to have a greater involvement in this project**, i.e. participating in more initiatives

"First they have to enlighten us, so that we can explain it to people."

"We have direct contact with the population and greater sensitivity that enables us to act locally."

"We have greater knowledge and proximity to the population and know what are the needs and beliefs..."

Decentralizing the information has a double advantage

- Spreading the right messages to many (the information goes to them and not the other way around)
- Providing relevant feedback to EDP in order to adapt plans and initiatives' development

"People give credit to Alcochete City Hall"

"People here are very parochial, we have 3 small parish councils and people prefer to have a direct contact."

Directly involving other stakeholders would have several advantages.

Stakeholders' involvement

"The information session was a good thing to do but there could be other decentralized actions... People can come with their neighbours who also want to know more about it."

- **Effectively teaching and spreading the (right) word** to the population, including the most problematic ones, **without having to send EDP teams door-to-door**
- **Receiving direct feedback** regarding specific areas and specific populations, allowing **a realistic perspective and finding out sooner what needs to be adjusted**

"Same way we teach people how to dress for a job interview or how to organize the family menu... we can also include this matter of electricity consumption."

"We need to make sure that people understand how that (the EDP Box) works."

"We can more easily mobilize people... Information sessions are for the well-informed and are only a few."

This closer contact might also **increase receptiveness towards EDP Box** and also contribute to a **more positive image of EDP** among the population. The close relationship between EDP and these Stakeholders that communicate EDP Box advantages near the population is also important for EDP collect the population feedback regarding EDP Box advantages in order to incorporate it on its internal processes.

At this point, the major challenges towards this project are related to the population lack of knowledge and incorrect expectations.

Stakeholders' involvement

Even though there was an EDP information session:

- Citizens aren't that much aware, nor talk much about this project;
- People feel there should be more information reaching end customers;
- Some cost reduction expectations weren't met;
- Specially the elderly feel a bit lost regarding technology.

"These new technologies just complicate life for people like us who have 80 years old (...) the elderly might be a bit crossed about all this... people don't now how to make the readings."

"The challenge is to attract peoples attention and get them to come to informative sessions."

The **EDP information session helped to answer some doubts** but only a small number of citizens attended.

Overall, all stakeholders feel they could have a greater role in this project, both in terms of connecting with the population and providing EDP with important feedback regarding people's reactions to it.

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All the InovGrid project initiatives undertaken by the City Hall together with EDP are seen as positive.

The information session was **useful** because it allowed people and less involved stakeholders to get **more information and to clarify some misunderstandings**.

There's however the need to overcome some challenges in order to make this sessions more efficient.

Challenges to overcome

- **Some people get inhibited because they think it's too formal and don't attend the meeting** – a solution could be to present this as an informal meeting suitable for everyone in Alcochete population
- **Distance**, as people that live on rural areas around the city hardly go there for that purpose – make sessions in more than one area
- **Technical language** – use less technical language as it is difficult to understand for older or less educated people
- **Focus the session more on practical information and less in the background of the project**

"It was quite good because the presidents of the parish councils came and they are normally who has a closer contact with people and the elderly."

"It was positive, I was enlighten regarding the reading."

"It was too theoretical for the purpose, people expected to understand a bit better about the meter they had at home and this was the last part of the session."

Stakeholders give some recommendations for future sessions and for the Conference in October.

Guidelines for possible future sessions and Conferences

- **Use a direct approach, by:**
 - Focusing more on **practical information / advantages** rather than technicalities;
 - Taking time to **show how to handle the equipment**, and let people try it for themselves;
 - Clearly defining **what can people expect and not;**
 - **Using a simple / not technical language**
 - **Give opportunity to ear people experience**
- **Don't give it a formal framework.** Announce the session in a way that can attract several segments of the population.
- **Enhance the session relevance** on the daily life.
- **Show the international acknowledgement and reward all the efforts done so far.**

"Give practical examples, advise people... not being too exhaustive, just explaining people how the box works, it's not necessary to know what happened before and how it as done..."

"To simplify contents... and approach only practical matters, what are the advantages? How can the person take full advantage and use from the EDP box."

"I would like them to present results, if they already have them."

S3C Game has potential to elicit greater participation among the younger population.

There's an overall agreement that **children can be a real help** when it comes to **introducing new habits and more energy efficient behaviours in the family**.

The **S3C game is seen as useful** in terms of educating the population, but there are some suggestions made by the stakeholders in order to improve it.

Some stakeholders who didn't belong to the education area weren't so much aware of it.

InovGrid Initiatives

Optimization of the S3C game to increase its potential

- Plan actions together with teachers and find useful ways of including the game in classes or adapted it to be part of the project area.
- Have also the participation of the parents, with:
 - prizes for adults (ex. a discount provided by the supplier , in the next electricity invoice);
 - platforms that make it more convenient / easier to participate (ex. a mobile phone APP).

"In a second stage I would focus more on families who lost part of their income (crisis) and need to be re-educated..."

"The whole family could play and win prizes, not just the children... One of the prizes could be a discount in the electricity bill."

The exposition “*A eletricidade em Alcochete: uma história, um futuro*” was relevant as it remembered people of Alcochete of their past and traditions.

The exposition was perceived as a way of **recognizing Alcochete people**.
And, in this sense most stakeholders, refer to it as a **positive initiative**.

“It portrays Alcochete tradition and its role regarding electricity throughout the years, since the 50s and 60s because then electric centrals used coal to produce electricity... We are a very proud people and like to preserve our traditions.”

“The people of Alcochete are very proud ... and almost all of us had a uncle or a grandfather that worked there... it has strengthen the bonds between EDP and Alcochete.”

But to increase the affluence of visitors and the word-of-mouth, it would be important to:

- Bring it to schools, so that teachers can organize visits and speak about it during class;
- Bring it to parish councils in order to allow a easy access to it and see it.

“They could bring the exposition here to school, and then teachers bring the classes to see it.”

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Overall, stakeholders define increasing information and reassuring that everything goes as planned to the general population as the main priority at this stage of the project.

As a future step of InovGrid project it's important to increase the information:

- Inform the population that the different functionalities of their **meters are already functioning**;
- Remind them of the **advantages for their daily life's** (e.g. no longer having estimates, greater control...);
- **Make sure they understand** (even when they first say everything is clear, might not be) and allow them to express their doubts;
- **Use clear and simple language and resort mainly to practical advise**;
- **Making them feel safe** (there is also some degree of anxiety towards any change or that their consumption data could be shared even without their permission and used for less licit actions).

"People are always going to prefer to ask neighbours or the parish president, in whom they trust."

City Hall and parish councils are willing to provide help since they believe it is in the people's best interest.

Their help is precious since it will prevent EDP from having to send workers to inform people door-to-door.

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Suggestions to increase stakeholders engagement in the project

So What?

To whom?

Initiatives/actions

- **Greater participation in the community and communication of the project**
- **Be open about the difficulties and discuss plans with the executive; Inform with greater advance to allow preparation**
- **Research results of the implemented actions**

Description and examples

- Sponsoring local parties, concerts and events
- Helping local institutions (e.g. firefighters)
- Help developing local tourism
- Support when applying for European funds that support measures of energy efficiency
- Public buildings' certification and more cost effective public equipment
- Electric Minibus transport children and the elderly
- Financial and social impact of the new meters

What?

- **Promote several ways of reaching and engaging the population**
- **Develop actions together with stakeholders to reach different target groups**
- **Promoting actions to reduce the electricity bill of public institutions or incentive microgeneration**

- Meeting with parish councils to help them organize and implement smaller and more informal local information sessions
- Provide other supportive means, like information included in the EDP invoices, call centre, to manage populations doubts
- Have a more regular contact with the City Hall specific sectors and schools in order to develop specific initiatives for different target groups, specially the elderly and rural /less educated population
- Closer work with schools – e.g. it could be used as a theme for project
- Foundations and schools might be interested in photovoltaic energy and solar panels

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Suggestions to increase population engagement in the project

So What?

To whom?

Initiatives /actions

- **Global events able to attract a large number of people**
- **Specific actions - different approaches for different target groups**
 - **Elderly**
 - **Children and teens**
 - **Rural areas**
 - **Lower social classes**

Description and examples

- Visible presence and sponsorships at local events (and there are many in Alcochete) – e.g. Kite festival, local festivities (Barrete Verde)
- Support local entities that people value like fireman, local associations, day centres
- Introduce InovGrid project in some school disciplines (Geography, English, Project area) and activities, across all year, including the smaller children
- A series of useful and free workshops - about healthy lifestyle, domestic economy, saving water and electricity
- Inform all the City Hall workers (City Hall is the major employer of the region)

What?

- **Leisure activities**
- **Cultural activities**
- **Sport activities**
- **Short but effective information sessions and simple presentations**
- **Gifts**

- A mailing properly identifying a party, open air concerts, a sunset or any other event where people of all ages can go and have fun with their families
- Contact local schools and parents so that teens and children can help explain to the elderly how the meters work and what are the advantages
- Gifts provided by the City Hall
- A mailing properly identified by the City hall and on a closed envelope - so people see it as important enough to open and read it (more effective vs. an email or a leaflet)
- Monitor electricity consumption peaks and proactively alerting and advising people (being pedagogic and showing that EDP has no interest in having people with a excessive consumption patterns – and communicate this)
- Demonstration sessions where local stakeholders share the positive impact on the community (ex. Environment)

Suggestions to increase population engagement in the project

	Initiatives	Description and examples	So What?
<p style="text-align: center;">How to communicate?</p>	<p>Urgently clarifying:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to use EDP Box • What are the advantages • How can they save money <p>• Inform when they start working</p> <p>• Attract people’s interest and willingness to listen</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informal and accurate but simple language, adapting it to the receptors • Informative, comprehensive but in a light pragmatic way – e.g. small presentation at the parish council or included in a broader themed event (e.g. dedicated to environment and healthy lifestyle, mobility week...) • Be available later to answer questions and doubts or being proactive and ask for feedback regarding things that are not working so well <p>• Through the call centre or pointing out the changes in their electricity invoice, for instance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lucidity is very important, people tend to come to places and events where they are sure to have fun • Offer prizes and gifts • Activities for children 	
	<p>• Use both personal contact / WOM and local means of communication</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Available means of communication - radio, City Hall website, local newspaper • Direct personal contact • Contact local communities (Alcochete as an impressive number of collectivities and local associations : ex. fire department, sports clubs, etc.) and work together with the City Hall in engaging them to help the population understand what they can benefit from these intelligent meters and not be afraid of them (they are not going to pay more) 	

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Stakeholders expect from EDP an innovative, progressive and responsible role in the future of the electricity sector in Portugal and an active role in providing a better service to people.

EDP's role

Besides continuing to be a **valuable partner** in future initiatives at Alcochete, stakeholders expect from EDP a **major role** at a national (and perhaps international) level.

The underlying idea is: as the main energy provider it has some degree of responsibility in terms of **innovation and also social responsibility** (regardless of now being a private sector company).

- Development of environmental sustainability and energy efficiency: information, technology, research
- Development of the renewable energy, make the best use of our natural resources (sun, wind, sea)
- Providing relevant information and educating people towards a more responsible and rational use of electricity
- Promoting greater environmental awareness by sponsoring and taking part of several initiatives directed to different target groups of the population
- Closer work with schools since younger generations are more prone to change and bring home the information
- Help people to decrease their electric bill and improve their lives (in a credible way, enhancing the humanity of EDP)

"EDP has all the necessary requirements to be a pioneer company."

"Has the capacity to innovate like no other, and can help think of ways of making the right decisions as an important economic agent in the energy area."

"Explaining to people how they can make a more intelligent use of the energy and also develop measures of environmental sustainability."

"Can have a very active role in changing behaviours of the citizens."

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Main objectives and methodology

Main research objective was to diagnose and to find ways of generating greater engagement of Alcochete Stakeholders with project InovGrid

- To understand how the different stakeholder perceive the energy theme, the project and the initiatives done so far by EDP in Alcochete
- To understand stakeholders experience and attitudes towards the project and how they see their role in it
- To gain access to degree of involvement with the project
- To evaluate the awareness and satisfaction level of the undertaken initiatives
- To understand how they perceive the role of EDP in this project, and what could be done to improve it
- To find out their perception about the population attitude and perceptions regarding this project, and find ways to engage different target groups / segments of Alcochete population
- What themes would they like to be approached at the next October conference
- How they envisage the role of EDP in the future (new products and services)

In this context, we had **10 In-depth interviews** (lasting approximately 1 h each) distributed in the following way:

- ***9 IDIs with Stakeholders (City Hall representatives, parish councils, school and foundation)***
- ***1 IDI with a consumer***

Stakeholders Engagement – S3C Project

Results of qualitative study

August, 2015